

ISUAAAT15-070

REDUCTION OF FORCED RESPONSE SENSITIVITY TO RANDOM MISTUNING VIA INTENTIONAL MISTUNING

Carlos Martel

Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
28040-Madrid, Spain

José J. Sánchez-Álvarez

Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
28040-Madrid, Spain

ABSTRACT

Intentional mistuning is a common procedure to decrease the uncontrolled vibration amplification effects of the inherent random mistuning and to reduce the sensitivity to it. The idea is to introduce an intentional mistuning pattern that is small but much larger than the existing random mistuning. The frequency of adjacent blades is moved apart by the intentional mistuning, reducing the effect of the blade-to-blade coupling and thus the effect of the random mistuning. The problem is analysed using the Asymptotic Mistuning Model methodology. A reduced order model is derived that allows us to understand the action mechanism of the intentional mistuning, and gives a simple expression for the estimation of its beneficial effect. The results from the reduced model are compared with those from the FEM simulation of two more realistic mistuned rotors.

INTRODUCTION

Mistuning refers to the unavoidable small differences between blades in a Turbomachinery rotor. Mistuning strongly influences the dynamical response of a bladed disk (see, e.g., the reviews [1,2]). In the case of forced response excitation, a blade mass scatter of the order of 2-3% can lead to the localization of the vibration to a few blades which can show response amplifications of 200%-300% [2]. These increased response levels result in a strong decrease of the fatigue life of the blades, and thus have a considerable negative impact on the safety, operability and readiness of aircraft turboengines.

One of the strategies that have been used in order to reduce the negative effect of the small random mistuning that is inevitably present in the rotor is the introduction of intentional mistuning. The idea is to implement in the rotor an intentional mistuning pattern that is kept small in size but large enough to overcome the existing random mistuning. The frequencies of adjacent blades are moved apart by the intentional mistuning, reducing the blade-to-blade interaction and thus the amplification potential of the random mistuning.

The benefits of intentional mistuning have been analyzed in many previous works [3-9], where a significant reduction of the mistuned response is reported together with a strong attenuation of the sensitivity to the underlying random mistuning. But, on the other hand, when a simple alternate intentional mistuning pattern is introduced, the mistuned rotor can be regarded as a tuned rotor with a basic sector made of two blades, and the small random mistuning present in this new tuned rotor with half the number of sectors should produce also an amplification of the forced response; and this appears to be in contradiction with the results in the papers mentioned above.

The aim of this paper is to understand which are the conditions required for the intentional mistuning to actually reduce the negative effects of the existing small random mistuning on the forced response of a turbomachinery rotor. To this end a reduced order model is first derived using the Asymptotic Mistuning Model (AMM) methodology. The AMM equations are used to study the effect of intentional mistuning, and the results and predictions obtained are then verified against full FEM simulations of two mistuned rotors.

NOMENCLATURE

TW	Travelling Wave
IBPA	InterBlade Phase Angle
IBR	Integrally Bladed Rotor
AMM	Asymptotic Mistuning Model
FEM	Finite Element Model
N	number of sectors
A_j	amplitude of mode j
ω	forcing frequency
r	forcing engine order
ω_j	elastic frequency of mode j
ξ	material damping
ω_0	averaged modal family frequency
δ_j	mistuning Fourier coefficient j
x_j	displacement of blade j
d_j	blade mistuning coefficient j

D	amplitude of the intentional mistuning
a_j	influence coefficient j
m_j	IBR mistuning of sector j
A_{im}	IBR intentional mistuning amplitude
ND	number of nodal diameters.

AMM FORMULATION

The Asymptotic Mistuning Model (AMM) methodology is used to derive a very reduced order model that describes the forced response of a blade dominated modal family in a mistuned bladed disk.

The AMM, expressed in terms of the amplitudes of the Travelling Wave (TW) modes $\mathbf{A}=(A_1, \dots, A_N)$ of the family, can be written as (see [10-12] for a detailed explanation):

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta\omega_1 - \Delta\omega + i\xi & \delta_1 & \dots & \delta_{N-1} \\ \delta_{N-1} & \Delta\omega_2 - \Delta\omega + i\xi & \dots & \delta_{N-2} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \delta_1 & \dots & \delta_{N-1} & \Delta\omega_N - \Delta\omega + i\xi \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} A_1 \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ A_N \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \vdots \\ i\xi \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

where $\Delta\omega=(\omega-\omega_0)/\omega_0$ is the relative deviation of the forcing frequency (ω) with respect to the mean value of the frequency for the modal family (ω_0), $\Delta\omega_1, \dots, \Delta\omega_N$ are the relative deviations of the modal frequencies with respect to ω_0 , and ξ represents the material damping of the TW modes. The mistuning is contained in the off-diagonal coefficients $\delta_1, \dots, \delta_{N-1}$, and the forcing takes the form of a TW with engine order r , which has been rescaled to have tuned response equal to 1.

The effect of the intentional mistuning is better analyzed if we change the AMM from the TW basis \mathbf{A} to the blade displacement basis $\mathbf{X}=(x_1, \dots, x_N)$, with the transformation

$$\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{PA}, \text{ with } \mathbf{P} = \begin{bmatrix} e^{i(\frac{2\pi 1}{N})1} & \dots & e^{i(\frac{2\pi N}{N})1} \\ \vdots & & \vdots \\ e^{i(\frac{2\pi 1}{N})j} & \dots & e^{i(\frac{2\pi N}{N})j} \\ \vdots & & \vdots \\ e^{i(\frac{2\pi 1}{N})N} & \dots & e^{i(\frac{2\pi N}{N})N} \end{bmatrix}$$

The resulting equations for the AMM in terms of the blade displacements take the form:

$$\begin{bmatrix} a_N - \Delta\omega + d_1 & a_1 & \dots & a_{N-1} \\ a_{N-1} & a_N - \Delta\omega + d_2 & \dots & a_{N-2} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_1 & \dots & a_{N-1} & a_N - \Delta\omega + d_N \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ x_N \end{bmatrix} = i\xi \begin{bmatrix} e^{i(\frac{2\pi r}{N})1} \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ e^{i(\frac{2\pi r}{N})N} \end{bmatrix}$$

where the coefficients d_1, \dots, d_N are the inverse Fourier transform of the mistuning coefficients $\delta_1, \dots, \delta_N$ (and they

now correspond to the physical frequency mistuning of the blades), and the off-diagonal coefficients a_1, \dots, a_N correspond to the inverse Fourier transform of the frequency corrections of the modal family: $\Delta\omega_1 + i\xi, \dots, \Delta\omega_N + i\xi$. (and represent the influence coefficients of the elastic structural coupling effects).

The lumped system derived above for the blade displacements exactly preserves the details of the elastic frequency of the modal family under consideration. It is interesting to note that in the original rotor one blade is only coupled to the adjacent ones through the disk, but in the lumped system there could be elastic coupling with blades that are further apart (through the coupling coefficients a_2, a_3, \dots).

LIMIT OF LARGE INTENTIONAL MISTUNING

The mistuning coefficient of each blade is now assumed to have a random part plus an intentional part. An asymptotic expansion is performed in the AMM lumped system above to calculate the interesting limit of intentional mistuning amplitude much larger than that of the random mistuning.

In order to make this derivation easier to follow, a simple alternate intentional mistuning pattern in a rotor with an even number of blades is considered (the results can be directly extrapolated to more complicated intentional mistuning patterns).

The AMM lumped system with the alternate intentional mistuning included takes the form

$$\begin{bmatrix} a_N - \Delta\omega + d_1 + D & a_1 & \dots & a_{N-1} \\ a_{N-1} & a_N - \Delta\omega + d_2 - D & \dots & a_{N-2} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_1 & \dots & a_{N-1} & a_N - \Delta\omega + d_N - D \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ x_N \end{bmatrix} = i\xi \begin{bmatrix} e^{i(\frac{2\pi r}{N})1} \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ e^{i(\frac{2\pi r}{N})N} \end{bmatrix}$$

where d_j corresponds to the amplitude of the random mistuning of blade j , and D is the amplitude of the alternate intentional pattern.

The intentional mistuning is now assumed to be much larger than the random mistuning and the elastic coupling and damping

$$|D| \gg |d_j|, |a_j|,$$

and the system above simplifies, in first approximation, to the homogeneous system:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta\omega + D & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \Delta\omega - D & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & \Delta\omega - D \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ x_N \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

This indicates that, when the intentional mistuning is dominating, the odd blades resonate at frequency $\Delta\omega=-D$, and the even blades resonate at $\Delta\omega=D$, with arbitrary blade displacements:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ 0 \\ x_3 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ x_{N-1} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ x_2 \\ 0 \\ x_4 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \\ x_N \end{bmatrix}$$

In other words, we recover the well known result that the main effect of the alternate intentional mistuning pattern is to split the resonance frequency of even and odd blades.

In order to see the detail of the resonance peaks we have to go to next order in the perturbative procedure. Near the resonance of the odd blades the forcing frequency is written as $-\Delta$ plus a small correction

$$\Delta\omega = -\Delta + \widetilde{\Delta\omega} + \dots$$

This expression is taken to the AMM lumped system and only the displacements of the odd blades are kept because the resonance peak of the even blades is now at a very distant frequency $\Delta\omega=\Delta$.

The resulting reduced system near the odd blades frequency peak is given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} a_N - \widetilde{\Delta\omega} + d_1 & a_2 & \dots & a_{N-2} \\ a_{N-2} & a_N - \widetilde{\Delta\omega} + d_3 & \dots & a_{N-4} \\ & \ddots & \ddots & \\ a_2 & \dots & a_{N-2} & a_N - \widetilde{\Delta\omega} + d_{N-1} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_3 \\ \vdots \\ x_{N-1} \end{bmatrix} = i\xi \begin{bmatrix} e^{i(\frac{2\pi r}{N})1} \\ e^{i(\frac{2\pi r}{N})3} \\ \vdots \\ e^{i(\frac{2\pi r}{N})(N-1)} \end{bmatrix}$$

Now the odd blades are only coupled among them through the influence coefficients a_2, a_4, \dots , indicating that the split in frequency produced by the alternate mistuning pattern has cancelled the coupling between adjacent blades; that is, the coefficient a_1 no longer appears in the blade motion equations.

The material damping appears only in the coefficient a_N in the diagonal

$$a_N = \frac{1}{N} \sum_1^N \Delta\omega_k + i\xi$$

The only way to make the system above not sensitive to the random mistuning of the odd blades (d_1, d_3, \dots) is to have a damping much larger than the terms outside the diagonal (a_2, a_4, \dots).

If this is the case, then the system is approximately diagonal, and the displacement of the blades is given by

$$x_j = \frac{i\xi e^{i(\frac{2\pi r}{N})j}}{a_N - \widetilde{\Delta\omega} + d_j},$$

which reaches a maximum value of

$$|x_j|_{\max} = 1$$

at the forcing frequency

$$\widetilde{\Delta\omega} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_1^N \Delta\omega_k + d_j$$

So, when the intentional mistuning is large as compared to the random mistuning the tuned amplification is recovered, and, what is perhaps more important, the sensitivity to random mistuning is severely reduced (the corresponding analysis for the even blades is completely similar).

The results in this section regarding the beneficial effect of intentional mistuning in a blade dominated modal family can be summarized as follows: (i) the coupling among the blades takes place through the elastic influence coefficients a_1, a_2, a_3, \dots , (ii) the intentional mistuning pattern has to be designed to remove the most relevant coupling, and (iii) the damping has to be large as compared to the remaining coupling among the blades of the same type. If all these conditions are met, then it can be ensured that the intentional mistuning pattern will be effective in reducing the vibration amplitude to the tuned value, and attenuating the sensitivity to random mistuning.

In the next two section several simulations of the forced response of two mistuned rotors A and B will be performed to verify this results, and to explore the limits of the AMM predictions.

ROTOR A SIMULATIONS

Rotor A has $N=24$ sectors and it is shown in Fig.1. The FEM description used has approximately 5.800 DOF per sector, and the forced response of the complete blisk (~ 140.000 DOF) can be computed in a reasonable time.

Figure 1: Rotor A

The tuned vibration characteristics of Rotor A are represented in Fig.2. The forcing of the first modal family is analysed, with an engine order $EO=8$.

Figure 2: Rotor A natural vibration frequencies (red thick line indicates the forcing)

The material damping is modelled by changing the full FEM stiffness matrix:

$$\mathbf{K} \rightarrow (1 + i\xi) \mathbf{K},$$

and the mistuning is implemented as a small variation of the mass matrix of each blade

$$\mathbf{M}_{\text{blade}j} \rightarrow (1 + m_j) \mathbf{M}_{\text{blade}j},$$

where m_1, \dots, m_N is the mistuning distribution.

A zoom of the frequencies of the first modal family is represented in the top plot of Fig. 3; it is the relative variation of the frequencies with respect to the average frequency ω_0 what is actually plotted $\Delta\omega_k = (\omega_k - \omega_0) / \omega_0$. And the corresponding influence coefficients associated with the elastic coupling a_1, \dots, a_N (the inverse Fourier transform of the $\Delta\omega_k$ distribution) are shown in the lower plot (with the damping removed from the coefficient $a_N = a_0$).

Figure 3: Top: relative frequency deviations for the first modal family of Rotor A. Bottom: corresponding influence coefficients (with the damping removed from the coefficient $a_N = a_0$).

It can be clearly seen in Fig. 3 that the main coupling comes from the coefficient a_1 , which corresponds to the coupling of one blade with the directly adjacent ones. In

this case an alternate mistuning pattern is expected to give optimal results.

The mistuning distributions that are going to be tested are composed of a random pattern with zero average and maximum amplitude 3%, and an alternate mistuning pattern $[1, -1, \dots, 1, -1]$ with amplitude A_{im} in the range 0-10%.

The material damping is set to $\xi=0.01$, which is much larger than the remaining coupling coefficients once a_1 is cancelled by the alternate mistuning pattern (see Fig. 3). In this case, the intentional mistuning should be able to reduce the vibration amplitude and the sensitivity to random mistuning.

The vibration amplitude for 5 different random mistuning patterns is presented in Fig.4. It can be seen how the vibration amplitude is reduced to the tuned value as the amplitude of the intentional mistuning is increased from $A_{im}=0\%$ to $A_{im}=10\%$. The sensitivity to the random mistuning is also strongly attenuated, as predicted by the AMM theory in the previous section.

Figure 4: Maximum vibration amplitude for increasing intentional mistuning amplitude and 5 different random mistuning patterns.

The frequency sweeps and the blade displacements for one of the random patterns is represented in Fig. 5. As the amplitude of the intentional mistuning grows there is a split in the resonance curve into two peaks, one for the odd and one for the even blades, and the amplification of the vibration is decreased. In the case of $A_{im}=10\%$, the even and odd blades are effectively decoupled and, at the maximum, only the even blades have a large vibration amplitude.

Figure 5: Frequency sweep and blade displacement at the maximum for $A_{im}=0\%$ (top), $A_{im}=5\%$ (middle), and $A_{im}=10\%$ (bottom).

In order to highlight the importance of the separation in frequency of the adjacent blades, a second mistuning pattern is now implemented that is similar to the alternate but with the last two blades identical:

$$[1, -1, \dots, 1, -1, 1, 1]$$

This pattern leaves three consecutive blades (the first and the two last ones) with the same intentional mistuning, that is, three consecutive blades that are not separated in frequency.

The damping is kept at the same value as before $\xi=0.01$, and the same 5 random mistuning patterns are used for the computation of the forced response. The results are presented in Fig.6, which shows a much smaller reduction of the vibration amplitude, and a much larger sensitivity to random mistuning than in the previous case.

Moreover, in the corresponding frequency sweeps in Fig.7, it can be appreciated that, as expected, the maximum displacement takes place at the three consecutive identical blades.

Figure 6: Maximum vibration amplitude for increasing intentional mistuning amplitude and 5 different random mistuning patterns.

Figure 7: Frequency sweep and blade displacement at the maximum for $A_{im}=0\%$ (top), $A_{im}=5\%$ (middle), and $A_{im}=10\%$ (bottom).

ROTOR B SIMULATIONS

Rotor B is shown in Fig.8; it has $N=21$ sectors, and the used FEM has 3.588 DOF per sector, with a total number of approximately 75.000 DOF for the full rotor.

Figure 8: Rotor B.

The frequency versus ND diagram for the tuned rotor B is plotted in Fig. 9, with the EO=8 forcing of the first modal family indicated.

Figure 9: Rotor B natural vibration frequencies (red thick line indicates the forcing).

The frequency deviations and the elastic coupling influence coefficients for the first modal family of Rotor B are presented in Fig. 10. Now the coupling coefficients a_2 and a_3 have both a value that is not negligible as compared to the material damping $\xi=0.01$. Following the AMM theory, an effective intentional mistuning pattern should now separate one blade from its two adjacent ones in order to remove the effect of the coupling induced by the coefficients a_2 and a_3 .

Figure 10: Top: relative frequency deviations for the first modal family of Rotor A. Bottom: corresponding influence coefficients (with the damping removed from the coefficient $a_N=a_0$).

The intentional mistuning pattern selected for the computations of the forced response of Rotor B is thus taken to be of the form:

$$[1,0,-1,1,0,-1,\dots,1,0,-1]$$

with amplitude A_{im} , and with the same random mistuning patterns as in the Rotor A case, but with 4% amplitude.

Figure 11: Maximum vibration amplitude for increasing intentional mistuning amplitude and 5 different random mistuning patterns.

The resulting maximum vibration amplitude for increasing intentional mistuning amplitude is shown in Fig.11. Again the intentional mistuning pattern is effective: it clearly reduces the vibration amplification and the sensitivity to random mistuning.

This pattern is less effective than the alternate pattern for Rotor B (see Fig.4) because: (i) the net difference in terms of intentional mistuning between adjacent blades was $2A_{im}$ for the alternate pattern and now is smaller, only A_{im} , and (ii) the remaining coupling coefficients after applying the intentional mistuning pattern have now higher amplitude (compare a_3 in Fig.10 with a_2 in Fig.3).

Figure 12: Frequency sweep and blade displacement at the maximum for $A_{im}=0\%$ (top), $A_{im}=5\%$ (middle), and $A_{im}=10\%$ (bottom).

The corresponding frequency sweeps are plotted in Fig. 12. The main difference with the case of the alternate mistuning pattern is that, for large intentional mistuning, the resonance curve is now split into three peaks, and the blade displacement at the maximum shows larger motion in one blade out of every three, indicating that there are three types of blades decoupled by the intentional mistuning pattern.

In order to see the importance of the relative value of the damping compared to the remaining coupling coefficient a_3 , a new set of forced response simulations is performed on Rotor B leaving unchanged all parameters except for the value of the material damping that is reduced to $\xi=0.001$. Note that the material damping is now comparable to the remaining coupling coefficient a_3 (see Fig.10), and therefore, according to the AMM theory, the intentional mistuning pattern is not necessarily going to have any beneficial effects in this case.

Figure 13: Maximum vibration amplitude for increasing intentional mistuning amplitude and 5 different random mistuning patterns.

Figure 14: Frequency sweep and blade displacement at the maximum for $A_{im}=0\%$ (top), $A_{im}=5\%$ (middle), and $A_{im}=10\%$ (bottom).

The vibration amplitude for this case with reduced material damping is shown in Fig.13. No clear trend of vibration amplitude reduction can be appreciated, and the sensitivity to random mistuning is now much higher than in the previous simulations with larger material damping presented in Fig. 11. The corresponding frequency sweeps plotted in Fig.15 exhibit now much sharper peaks because of the reduced damping. There is still a split in frequency in three groups of peaks, but the blade displacements at the maximum are now much more localized; a clear indication that the random mistuning has now a strong effect on the blades of each type.

MAIN RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

The application of the AMM methodology allows to understand the way of using intentional mistuning to reduce the vibration amplification and the sensitivity to the unavoidable underlying random mistuning, and the limitations of this strategy.

The effective attenuation of the random mistuning effects using intentional mistuning is seen to depend on the relative value of three small effects: coupling of the modal family, blade damping, and the random mistuning amplitude:

- Blades are coupled through the elastic forces. The magnitude of this coupling is measured by the influence coefficients (a_k) associated with the frequency deviation of the modal family ($\Delta\omega_k$).
- The effect of the intentional mistuning is to separate in frequency the different types of blades, reducing the coupling between them.
- In order to attenuate the effect of random mistuning, the intentional mistuning pattern should first separate in frequency those blades that show a strong elastic coupling by the influence coefficients, and then, the damping of the modal family, ξ , should be much larger than the remaining influence coefficients.
- The AMM analysis gives also a very simple expression for the limit value of the maximum vibration amplitude that the blades can experience when the intentional mistuning is effective in uncoupling them:

$$|x_j|_{\max} = 1$$

(the tuned vibration amplitude).

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors wish to thank Prof. B. Epureanu and Dr. O. Khemiri for providing us with the FEM models of the blisks. This work has been supported by the Spanish Ministerio de Educación y Ciencia under grant DPI2017-84700-R, and by the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid under grant GI1514120024. CM wishes to thank also Industria de Turbopropulsores for its continued support.

REFERENCES

- [1] M.P. Castanier and C. Pierre. Modeling and analysis of mistuned bladed disk status and emerging directions. *Journal of Propulsion and Power*, 22(2):384–396, 2006.
- [2] D.J. Ewins and Y.J. Chan. Vibration of rotating bladed discs: Mistuning, coriolis, and robust design. In K. Gupta, editor, *Proceedings of the IUTAM Symposium on Emerging Trends in Rotor Dynamics*, pages 163–175. Springer, 2011.
- [3] D.J. Ewins. The effects of detuning upon the forced vibrations of bladed-disks. *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, 9(1):65–79, 1969.
- [4] Matthew Castanier and Christophe Pierre. Investigation of the combined effects of intentional and random mistuning on the forced response of bladed disks. *Joint Propulsion Conferences, AIAA-98-3720*. American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Jul 1998.
- [5] Marc P. Mignolet, Wei Hu, and Ioan Jadic. On the Forced Response of Harmonically and Partially Mistuned Bladed Disks. Part I. *Journal of Rotating Machinery*, 6(1):29–41, 2000.
- [6] Marc P. Mignolet, Wei Hu, and Ioan Jadic. On the Forced Response of Harmonically and Partially Mistuned. Part II. *International Journal of Rotating Machinery*, 6(1):43–56, 2000.
- [7] Matthew P. Castanier and Christophe Pierre. Using intentional mistuning in the design of turbomachinery rotors. *AIAA Journal*, 40(10):2077–2086, Oct 2002.
- [8] Sang-Ho Lim, Matthew P. Castanier, and Christophe Pierre. Intentional mistuning design space reduction based on vibration energy flow in bladed disks. Number 41715, pages 373–384, 2004.
- [9] Yun Han, Raghavendra Murthy, Marc P. Mignolet, and Jeff Lentz. Optimization of intentional mistuning patterns for the mitigation of the effects of random mistuning. *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, 136 (6):062505–062505–9, Feb 2014.
- [10] C. Martel and R. Corral. Asymptotic description of maximum mistuning amplification of bladed disk forced response. *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, 131:022506, 2009.
- [11] O. Khemiri, C. Martel, and R. Corral. Forced response of mistuned bladed disks: Asymptotic description and FEM validation. *AIAA Journal of Propulsion and Power*, 30:397–406, 2013.
- [12] C. Martel and J.J. Sánchez. Maximum mistuning amplification of the forced response vibration of turbomachinery rotors in the presence of aerodynamic damping. *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, 397, 108-122, 2017.

